

ZnFe₂O₄/MnFe₂O₄ incorporated in NaY zeolite: Facile fabrication and application of novel designed nanocomposite catalyst for the detoxification of sulfur mustard agent simulant

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Abstract

In this work, ZnFe₂O₄/MnFe₂O₄ nanoparticles were successfully incorporated in NaY zeolite via the ultrasonic-assisted hydrothermal method to obtain the novel ZnFe₂O₄/MnFe₂O₄@NaY nanocomposite catalyst and subsequently characterized by FE-SEM, EDX, FTIR, XRD, AFM and VSM techniques.

Then, the ZnFe₂O₄/MnFe₂O₄@NaY nanocomposite catalyst performance for the detoxification of sulfur mustard agent simulant 2-chloroethyl phenyl sulfide (2-CEPS) was evaluated by applying GC-FID analysis. The GC-FID achieved data displayed that this agent simulant was completely detoxified over the ZnFe₂O₄/MnFe₂O₄@NaY nanocomposite surface in n-octane solvent after contact time of 15 min. The both hydrolysis and elimination products namely 2-hydroxyl ethyl phenyl sulfide (2-HEPS) and phenyl vinyl sulfide (PVS) from 2-CEPS molecule were also identified by GC-MS analysis, respectively.

Keywords: ZnFe₂O₄/MnFe₂O₄@NaY, zeolite, nanocomposite, 2-CEPS, detoxification, hydrolysis, elimination.